

THE OBSERVED GAPS IN THE SELECTED LEARNING AREAS AMONG GRADE TWO LEARNERS IN THE THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR CRAFTING A LEARNING RECOVERY PLAN FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

This study identified the observed gaps among Grade 2 learners in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The researchers used a survey questionnaire to gather information and a quantitative design using statistical analysis to analyze the data from Grade 2 Teachers. The researchers used the Mean Percentage Rating of the first grading period of Grade 2 learners to determine the performance level in English, Filipino, and Mathematics subjects. The gaps observed were the following: Skills gaps, Motivation gaps, Environmental gaps, Communication gaps, Material gaps, Digital gaps, and Parental gaps. The study found no significant difference in the observed gaps in the selected learning areas. The performance of Grade 2 learners in English and Mathematics falls under fairly satisfactory while satisfactory in Filipino. There were gaps across the selected learning areas. The study suggested strategies and proposed a Learning Recovery Plan Framework to address the gaps observed.

Keywords: *observed gaps, performance, learning recovery plan*

INTRODUCTION

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Education in the Philippines implemented distance learning to ensure learning continuity. However, the DepEd recognizes the challenges of delivering alternative ways of learning to 27.7 million to ensure learning continuity. Given the challenges of distance learning and unequal access to resources, poor-performing, and marginalized students may fall further behind. (Yang and Beam 2021)

Since the pandemic had reached the Philippines, the schools were forced to conduct classes at a distance to ensure the safety of the pupils and the teachers against COVID-19 while providing learning continuity to the students. Learning at home does not guarantee a quality teaching-learning process. Different problems were met by the teachers and parents trying to maintain a stable learning environment, including schedule changes, technology integration, internet access, distribution of modules, medium of instruction; parents' capability to help pupils learn, and other home distractions. This disrupts pupils across all age groups, leaving them with a long-lasting effect on their learning. Different researches shows that these disruptions have led to many students experiencing gaps in their education throughout the distance learning pandemic.

For the past two years that the classes were interrupted, the opening of the classes revealed the pupils' low performance in the different learning areas, poor reading skills and comprehension, difficulty in following simple instructions, and poor writing skills. Pupils are below the level in their expected grade level. The result is now stressing the teachers on how they will handle learners from filling the learning gaps while introducing new topics in the class and much more in handling struggling learners.

The DepEd sought innovative strategies and crafting a learning recovery program to address gaps due to pandemic-related disruptions. The teachers are seeking the help of the schools to make interventions effective to help pupils catch up and accelerate their learning as we are now facing the result of class disruptions due to the pandemic. All parties need to be involved in developing strategies that can be useful in filling the learning gaps among pupils (Briones, 2022). The research will significantly help collect and extract ideas to make helpful and appropriate interventions for the current education needs and demands.

The researchers looked for guidance and solutions on handling the current classroom situation, became interested in addressing these issues since we are now in-person classes. Numerous studies have demonstrated that these difficulties cause significant gaps among students. Thus, the researchers developed this study to determine the gaps common among struggling pupils that may eventually lead to developing a learning recovery plan to fill the observed gaps in learning.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the observed gaps in selected learning areas among Grade 2 learners in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance level of Grade 2 learners based on the Mean Percentage Rating (MPR) in the first grading period in the following selected learning areas:
 - 1.1 English;
 - 1.2 Filipino; and
 - 1.3 Mathematics?

2. What are the observed gaps in learning in the selected learning areas that are observed among Grade 2 learners?

- 2.1 knowledge gaps;
- 2.2 skills gaps;
- 2.3 motivation gaps;
- 2.4 environmental gaps;
- 2.5 communication gaps;
- 2.6 material gaps;
- 2.7 digital gaps; and
- 2.8 parental gaps?

3. Is there a significant difference in the observed gaps in the selected learning areas?

4. What learning recovery plan framework could be proposed to address the observed gaps in learning?

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative design was employed to ensure the result of the research. This study used a descriptive type of research in which responses were gathered from the respondents using a survey questionnaire. The researcher believed this type of method could assist her in obtaining facts and knowledge regarding the performance level of Grade 2 learners and the gaps observed among them. Quezon is one of the provinces in CALABARZON, divided into four Congressional districts. The Third Congressional District of Quezon has 12 districts, namely Agdangan, Buenavista, Catanauan, General Luna, Padre Burgos, Pitogo, Macalelon, Mulanay, San Andres, San Francisco, San Narciso, and Unisan. The chosen respondents of this study were the teachers from the public elementary schools in the 12 districts of Bondoc Peninsula. This part of Quezon had schools in far-flung areas, and the modality of distance learning became uneasy to implement. The internet was not well established in most places in this area. The researcher is a teacher from the Third Congressional District of Quezon and wanted to contribute to the district's performance through this research. Grade 2 pupils were the subject of this study since distance learning had disrupted the two years of their education, which is the foundation of learning. The performance results in the selected discipline are alarming to the teacher. Likewise, the researchers believed that distance learning had mostly affected this grade level.

Thus, the purposive sampling technique was used, which targeted individuals with interest in the study. The researchers purposely chose grade two teachers, as teachers are the primary source of information for gathering data about learners' performance levels and the observed gaps among them.

The researchers used cluster random sampling to determine the included schools from medium and small schools and purposely chose large schools in each district in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. There were 12 grade two

teachers from small schools, 25 grade two teachers from medium schools, and 60 grade two teachers from large schools, with 97 Grade 2 teachers.

The researchers prepared a combination of adaptive and self-made survey questionnaires as the main instruments of the study. They formulated the instrument through reading journals and related studies. The researcher consulted her adviser for the revision and correction of some questions.

The instrument used in this study was composed of two parts: Part I – is the performance level of Grade 2 learners based on the Mean Percentage Rating (MPR) of the first grading result in selected learning areas, which are generally categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fair, and did not meet the expectation. Part II – consists of gaps in learning in the selected learning areas observed by Grade 2 teachers. The respondents checked the appropriate column for their chosen answer in the checklist type.

The researchers used the following scale to determine the performance level of Grade 2 learners with ratings and the corresponding indicators based on Department of Education Order No. 36, s.2016, p.4 summary of grades for classifying learners per learning areas.

5 – Point Likert Scale to measure the performance level of Grade 2 Learners in the selected learning areas.

Rating/grade	Indicator
90-100 %	Outstanding
85-89 %	Very Satisfactory
80-84 %	Satisfactory
75-79 %	Fairly Satisfactory
74 % -below	Did not Meet Expectation

For teachers' observation of gaps in learning among learners, the 5-point Likert Scale was used.

After formulating the instrument, the researchers finished the necessary revision and administered it to 10 people who were excluded from the list. After the instrument's validity had been tested and approved, the researchers reproduced it for distribution to the study's respondents.

This study involved the teachers handling Grade 2 pupils in public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon for the School Year 2022-2023.

Similarly, this study found the performance level of Grade 2 learners based on the Mean Percentage Rating of the first grading period in English, Filipino, and Mathematics, the observed gaps in learning by the teacher among Grade 2 learners in the selected learning areas. The observed gaps were knowledge, skills, environmental, motivation, communication, digital, material, and parental. Other gaps

not mentioned in the problem statement were excluded in the result. It was conducted during the School Year 2022-2023.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers sent a letter of permission from the DepEd Quezon Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study. After the approval, the validated questionnaire was personally distributed or emailed to the respondents.

For clarification, they informed the respondents about the purpose of the study and guided them accordingly for an efficient and effective accomplishment of the questionnaire and assured of the confidentiality of their answers. When all the teachers finished completing the questionnaire, the data gathered from the questionnaires were encoded, tallied, classified, tabulated, and statistically treated to answer the problems of the study. Findings were further analyzed and presented in tables for a better and easier presentation of the figures and more convenient and precise comparison results.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical treatment measured the gathered data:

Percentage was used to determine the performance level of Grade 2 learners based on the MPR of the first grading result in the selected learning areas. This tool was utilized to answer the statement of problem no.1.

Weighted Mean was used to determine the gaps in learning among Grade 2 learners as observed by their respective advisers in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. Mean values for the categories were computed. This statistical tool was beneficial to answer question number 2 in the statement of the problem.

The researchers used the Likert Scale for the purpose of interpretation. The following ranges were used for the gaps observed among pupils.

Scale	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Highly Observed	The gap can always be seen.
4	3.40 – 4.19	Highly Observed	The gap can often be seen.
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Observed	The gap can sometimes be seen.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Observed	The gap can rarely be seen.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Observed	The gap can never be seen.

The ANOVA was used for statistical analysis to compare the difference of the results in the observed gaps in each learning area. The analysis of variance provided answers in the statement of problem no. 3.

RESULTS

Part I. Performance Level of Grade 2 Learners in the First Grading Period in the Selected Learning Areas

Table 1

Performance of Grade 2 Learners in the First Grading Period in the Selected Learning Areas

Learning Areas	Level of Performance										Mean	DI
	O (90-100%)		VS (85-89%)		S (80-84%)		FS (75-79%)		DNME (74%-below)			
	F	%	F	%	F	%	f	%	f	%		
English	0	0.00	5	5.15	43	44.32	46	47.42	3	3.09	2.52	FS
Filipino	0	0.00	27	27.84	50	51.55	19	19.59	1	1.03	3.06	S
Mathematics	0	0.00	7	7.22	45	46.39	42	43.30	3	3.09	2.58	FS

Legend:

5–	4.20 – 5.00	Outstanding (O)
4–	3.40 – 4.19	Very Satisfactory (VS)
3–	2.60 – 3.39	Satisfactory (S)
2–	1.80 – 2.59	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)
1–	1.00 – 1.79	Did not Meet Expectation (DNME)

Descriptive Interpretation (DI)

Part II. Gaps Observed by the Teachers in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Table 2

Knowledge Gaps Observed by the Teachers in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
Familiarity with the lesson	3.75	HO	3.64	H O	3.73	HO	3.71	.733	HO
Providing insight about lesson	3.73	HO	3.59	H O	3.68	HO	3.67	.701	HO
In-depth knowledge about the lesson	3.69	HO	3.60	H O	3.71	HO	3.67	.721	HO
Understanding the lesson	3.81	HO	3.69	H O	3.78	HO	3.76	.721	HO
Retentive memory of the previous lesson	3.75	HO	3.59	H O	3.62	HO	3.65	.700	HO
Composite Mean	3.75	HO	3.62	HO	3.70	HO	3.69	.715	HO

Legend:

4.20 – 5.00	Very Highly Observed (VHO)
3.40 – 4.19	Highly Observed (HO)

2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
 1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
 1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
 Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
 Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 3

Skills Gaps Observed by the Teachers in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners.

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. Showing patience in doing activities	3.73	HO	3.72	HO	3.71	HO	3.72	.691	HO
2. Finishing simple activities on time	3.73	HO	3.69	HO	3.69	HO	3.70	.721	HO
3. Following teachers' instruction	3.66	HO	3.75	HO	3.68	HO	3.70	.746	HO
4. Completing their task and activities	3.74	HO	3.74	HO	3.72	HO	3.73	.789	HO
5. Reviewing and correcting their mistakes in the activity	3.72	HO	3.65	HO	3.61	HO	3.66	.764	HO
Composite Mean	3.72	HO	3.71	HO	3.68	HO	3.70	.742	HO

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Observed (VHO)
 3.40 – 4.19 Highly Observed (HO)
 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
 1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
 1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
 Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
 Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 4

Motivation Gaps Observed by the Teachers in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. Attentiveness in the lesson	3.72	HO	3.70	HO	3.71	HO	3.71	.704	HO
2. Exerting effort to improve their work	3.70	HO	3.70	HO	3.77	HO	3.72	.738	HO
3. Eagerness to learn and relearn	3.68	HO	3.73	HO	3.77	HO	3.73	.708	HO
4. Initiative in doing the task	3.77	HO	3.66	HO	3.66	HO	3.70	.732	HO

5. Interest in the lesson	3.75	HO	3.69	HO	3.70	HO	3.71	.727	HO
Composite Mean	3.72	HO	3.70	HO	3.72	HO	3.71	.722	HO

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Observed (VHO)
3.40 – 4.19 Highly Observed (HO)
2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 5
Environmental Gaps Observed by the Teachers in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. Distracted by the noise	3.44	HO	3.45	HO	3.62	HO	3.50	.896	HO
2. Comfortable inside the classroom.	3.49	HO	3.54	HO	3.62	HO	3.55	.879	HO
3. Satisfied with their seat	3.43	HO	3.46	HO	3.62	HO	3.50	.892	HO
4. At ease with the people inside the classroom.	3.49	HO	3.56	HO	3.64	HO	3.56	.854	HO
5. Asking help to the teacher and to their classmates.	3.69	HO	3.72	HO	3.82	HO	3.74	.790	HO
Composite Mean	3.51	HO	3.55	HO	3.66	HO	3.57	.862	HO

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Observed (VHO)
3.40 – 4.19 Highly Observed (HO)
2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 6

Communication Gaps Observed by the Teacher in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. Following simple instruction.	3.79	HO	3.70	HO	3.72	HO	3.74	.715	HO
2. Doing things based on the teacher's instruction.	3.85	HO	3.73	HO	3.71	HO	3.76	.711	HO
3. Asking for clarification of the lesson.	3.80	HO	3.70	HO	3.80	HO	3.77	.699	HO
4. Interacting with his/her peer during discussion and activities	3.76	HO	3.62	HO	3.69	HO	3.69	.734	HO
5. Attentiveness during discussion	3.73	HO	3.69	HO	3.74	HO	3.72	.715	HO
Composite Mean	3.79	HO	3.69	HO	3.73	HO	3.74	.715	HO

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Observed (VHO)
 3.40 – 4.19 Highly Observed (HO)
 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
 1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
 1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
 Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
 Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 7

Material Gaps Observed by the Teacher in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. Interacting with the lesson even without instructional materials.	3.61	HO	3.60	HO	3.60	HO	3.60	.719	HO
2. Engaging in a task even without manipulative materials	3.58	HO	3.55	HO	3.58	HO	3.57	.764	HO
3. Doing activity even though they have no school	3.57	HO	3.47	HO	3.52	HO	3.52	.749	HO

supplies to use inside the classroom.										
4. Copying and answering the written assessment	3.72	HO	3.58	HO	3.64	HO	3.65	.762	HO	
5. Remembering the past lesson even without note or take-home assignment	3.58	HO	3.53	HO	3.49	HO	3.53	.744	HO	
Composite Mean	3.51	HO	3.55	HO	3.57	HO	3.57	.748	HO	

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Observed (VHO)
3.40 – 4.19 Highly Observed (HO)
2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 8
Digital Gaps Observed by the Teachers in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. Participation in the discussion though without the use of power point presentation.	3.61	HO	3.63	HO	3.61	HO	3.62	.768	HO
2. Excitement in listening to the stories even without the use of video-recorded materials.	3.68	HO	3.71	HO	3.73	HO	3.71	.788	HO
3. Attentiveness when teacher depends on books during discussion.	3.58	HO	3.61	HO	3.53	HO	3.57	.778	HO
4. Interest in the lesson even without the use of learning support tools inside the classroom like tv set, computers, etc.	3.61	HO	3.64	HO	3.63	HO	3.63	.784	HO
5. Relatedness to the present situation	3.56	HO	3.54	HO	3.56	HO	3.55	.757	HO

and new trends
even without gadget
to be used at home.

Composite Mean	3.61	HO	3.61	HO	3.61	HO	3.62	.775	HO
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Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Observed (VHO)
 3.40 – 4.19 Highly Observed (HO)
 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
 1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
 1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
 Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
 Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 9
Parental Gaps Observed by the Teachers in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. Doing take home assignment even without the help of parents or guardians.	3.63	HO	3.66	HO	3.64	HO	3.64	.745	HO
2. Participation in school activities even parents is not active in school.	3.61	HO	3.54	HO	3.53	HO	3.56	.689	HO
3. Eagerness to study even without parents' support.	3.61	HO	3.58	HO	3.51	HO	3.57	.674	HO
4. Improvement even parents aren't involved.	3.46	HO	3.48	HO	3.41	HO	3.45	.715	HO
5. Daily attendance even without supervision of parents.	3.49	HO	3.47	HO	3.48	HO	3.48	.794	HO
Composite Mean	3.56	HO	3.55	HO	3.51	HO	3.54	.723	HO

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Observed (VHO)
 3.40 – 4.19 Highly Observed (HO)
 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
 1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
 1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
 Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
 Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 10

Summary Table of the Gaps Observed in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Indicators	English		Filipino		Mathematics		Total		
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	SD	DI
Knowledge Gaps	3.75	HO	3.62	HO	3.70	HO	3.69	.715	HO
Skills Gaps	3.72	HO	3.71	HO	3.68	HO	3.70	.742	HO
Motivation Gaps	3.72	HO	3.70	HO	3.72	HO	3.71	.722	HO
Environmental Gaps	3.51	HO	3.55	HO	3.66	HO	3.57	.862	HO
Communication Gaps	3.79	HO	3.69	HO	3.73	HO	3.74	.715	HO
Material Gaps	3.51	HO	3.55	HO	3.57	HO	3.57	.748	HO
Digital Gaps	3.61	HO	3.63	HO	3.61	HO	3.62	.775	HO
Parental Gaps	3.56	HO	3.55	HO	3.51	HO	3.54	.723	HO
Grand Mean	3.65	HO	3.63	HO	3.65	HO	3.64	.750	HO

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Observed (VHO)
 3.40 – 4.19 Highly Observed (HO)
 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed (MO)
 1.80 – 2.59 Less Observed (LO)
 1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed (NO)
 Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
 Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 11

Statistical Table Showing the Significant Difference in the Gaps Observed in the Selected Learning Areas

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	.067	2	.034	.117	.889	Not Significant	Ho not rejected
Within Groups	82.528	288	.287				
Total	82.595	290					

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the performance of Grade 2 learners based on the Mean Percentage Rating (MPR) in the first grading period in the selected learning areas.

The presented data revealed that Grade 2 learners have almost similar performance (Fairly Satisfactory) in English and Math while a satisfactory performance in Filipino.

Data revealed that the Grade 2 learners are still adjusting to various activities in the selected learning areas, especially in English and Mathematics, from pandemic to face-to-face classes, which results in low achievement rates to attain the instructional objectives and targets for each learning competency.

According to teacher-respondents, Grade 2 learners have low reading skills, low numeracy skills, low writing skills and low reading comprehension. These affects the learners' academic performance. Grade 2 learners have also noticed a drop in grades and low performances. This is evident in their character, behavior, learning style and assessment. They struggle to follow instructions, lack attention, have poor memory recall, and struggle to learn and retain the lesson due to a lack of comprehension.

With this result, the difficulties of remote learning and unequal access to resources might cause underachieving and underprivileged students to lag even further (Yang & Beam 2021). The achievement gap has increased significantly for kids of all ages, with various threats in each age group. Equity for Children.org (2020).

According to some studies (Azucena et al., 2022; Pentang et al., 2020), Filipino students score poorly or unsatisfactorily in Mathematics. In the study of (Bielinski et al., 2020), they suggested that students are likely to return to school in the fall of 2020 with less developed reading and math skills than typical at each grade level in prior years. Similarly, (Cohodes et al., 2022) cited that learning delays are closely related to the time students spend out of school or in remote instruction.

Part II. Gaps Observed by the Teachers in the Selected Learning Areas Among Grade 2 Learners

Table 2 presents the three areas of knowledge gaps among Grade 2 learners. The knowledge gap was *highly observed* in almost all indicators including familiarity with the lessons, having insights on the lesson, in-depth knowledge about the lesson, in understanding the lesson, and in retention.

Based on the findings, Grade 2 learners have no retentive recall of the prior session and are unfamiliar with it, particularly in English and Mathematics. This knowledge gap has an impact on their understanding and acquiring in-depth knowledge of the lesson, thus affecting their performance.

Reimers (2021) listed some challenges to learning, including a lack of knowledge about success or mistakes in the activities, a lack of comprehension of what one is doing, a lack of learning and understanding, and the belief that one lacks the information required to go to the next grade. Children are confined to their homes and have little to no access to learning, which significantly impacts them. Insufficient instruction throughout the school years (ages 6 to 18) might impact children's cognitive development and future performance and learning on the job.

Table 3 presents the skills gaps among Grade 2 learners in the selected learning areas.

Although the following statements under skills gaps were *highly observed*, the gap in completing their task has the highest mean of 3.73. The mean scores for each subject area showed a highly skills gap: 3.72 for English, 3.71 for Filipino, 3.72 and 3.68 for Mathematics. The composite mean of knowledge gaps is 3.7, with a standard deviation of 0.742, which means that skills gaps were *highly observed* across learning areas.

It can be inferred that Grade 2 children have skills gap in English, Filipino, and Mathematics subjects. They cannot complete activities on time because they cannot follow basic teacher instructions. It was also discovered that they lack patience when performing their tasks, reviewing, and correcting their mistakes.

When education has grown distant, it is challenging to preserve the discipline children learn while getting ready for school, participating in numerous activities, and utilizing various methods to learn their subjects in class. The seriousness that a teacher's physical presence can impart to their students appears impossible to achieve with online learning.

Bhamani et al. (2020) stated that students in this group spent more time on formative assessment activities during the lockdown than the previous year's cohort, probably compensating for the absence of classroom engagement. Schult et al. (2022).

Thus, despite the skills gaps becoming a global issue, there may be significant regional differences in the gap's precise characteristics and the policy options available to close it.

Table 4 reveals the motivation gaps among Grade 2 learners in the selected learning areas.

It could be deduced from the data given that motivation gap is high in English, Filipino, and Math. This could mean that the Grade 2 learners lack motivation in the subjects identified.

These data imply that there is a need to increase student motivation, particularly in English, Filipino, and Mathematics subjects. The teacher should try and use research-based instructional strategies to pique the learners' interest in the class, get them to complete their tasks, and improve their work. Several strategies can also be used to keep Grade 2 students focused.

Based on the study by Zaccoletti et al. (2020), it may have been challenging for children with disadvantaged conditions to learn because social isolation affects academic motivation. (Briones et al., 2021) noted that several factors influencing students' results were considered. Some of these include the traits of students, such as laziness, which is a widespread issue in today's youth, internet access, and lack of motivation. Additionally, the environment and the students' motivation affect their performance in class. While parents should encourage and support their children, the effectiveness of the teacher's teaching, the materials she chooses, and her communication with the students all directly impact how the students learn.

Table 5 shows the environmental gaps among Grade 2 learners in the selected learning areas.

In terms of the environmental gap, being comfortable in asking for help from the teacher and classmates is the most observable, with a mean of 3.74. The following means for each subject area, the environmental gaps were highly observed: 3.51 for English, 3.55 for Filipino, and 3.66 for Mathematics. The composite mean of

knowledge gaps across all learning areas is 3.57, and the standard deviation is 0.862, indicating that environmental gaps were highly observed.

A conducive learning environment and atmosphere promotes learning, encourages collaboration, and fosters the development of positive relationships. Meanwhile, Grade 2 learners experienced environmental gaps due to noise, distraction, and discomfort. They are uncomfortable in the classroom and are too hesitant to seek assistance from the teacher or their classmates.

There is a significant impact of creative learning spaces on student achievement, confidence, resilience, motivation, problem-solving, interpersonal skills, and attendance at school. Meanwhile, (Aristovnik et al., 2020) found that the learning environment had an impact on student satisfaction.

The communication gaps among Grade 2 students in the selected learning areas are shown in Table 6.

The data presented manifest that environmental gap *highly observed* in those subject areas mentioned. With the mean scores of 3.69 for Filipino, 3.79 for English, and 3.73 for Mathematics, the communication gap was *highly observed* in each subject area. The composite mean of knowledge gaps across all learning areas is 3.74, and the standard deviation is 0.715, indicating that there were considerable communication gaps.

Grade 2 students face communication gaps in three academic areas, particularly English. It was due to their inattention during the discussion and inability to follow simple instructions. They also have little interaction with their peers during discussions and activities. They are also hesitant to ask for clarification on the lesson.

Andrew et al. (2020) claimed that learning and instruction were modified to a context where students talked with their instructors and peers by phone or the Internet instead of face-to-face interaction, and learning was sometimes conducted through radio or television. According to the findings of (Dargo and Dimas 2021), teachers were unable to tell whether their students understood the lesson because there was insufficient communication to explain and help the students, which caused the students to lose interest in learning and become lazy by completing too many of the activities in the learning modules.

The material gaps among Grade 2 students in the selected areas of learning are shown in Table 7.

The following statements under "Material Gaps" were *highly observed*. The material gap was moderately observed with the following means for each subject area: 3.51 for English, 3.55 for Filipino, and 3.57 for Mathematics. With a standard deviation of 0.748 and a composite mean of 3.57, material gaps were *highly observed* across all learning areas.

Instructional resources are an essential component of the teaching and learning process. Grade 2 students had material gaps because they had limited involvement with the lesson, even without instructional materials, and low participation in a task without manipulative items given by the teacher. They are unable to complete their

activities because they lack school supplies. Many struggled to copy and respond to the written assessment given by the teacher, and many could not even recall the previous lesson without notes or take-home assignments.

Using superior supplementary resources can aid students in making connections between concepts. These learning materials should be developed to enable interactive learning where students' activities can be more engaging to learn better. Boardworks (2021).

In the study of Munastiwi and Puryono (2021), they mentioned that most teachers had difficulties developing interactive educational materials and carrying out evaluations. Due to the lack of resources for online learning, children struggled.

Table 8 reveals the digital gaps among Grade 2 learners in the selected learning areas.

Each statement under digital gaps was *highly observed*. The digital gap was *highly observed* in each subject area with the following mean: English, 3.61; Filipino, 3.63; Mathematics, 3.61.

The composite mean of knowledge gaps is 3.62 with a standard deviation of 0.775, which means that digital gaps were *highly observed* across learning areas.

The usage of ICT educational platforms improves learning and promotes an active learning environment. However, grade 2 students experienced digital gaps because they could not participate in class discussions without the teacher's use of Power Point presentations. They are not engaged in listening to stories if video recordings are not used. Furthermore, they are inattentive, with a lack of interest, and are unable to relate to new trends and current events if digital devices such as television, computers, and other gadgets are not used.

Parents, teachers, and students encountered challenges and difficulties setting up study spaces, test runs, learning routines, ways to stay updated with the teacher, healthy mindsets, and well-being while attending the new standard classes during the pandemic because not everyone has access to the internet or has devices for blended learning, Childhope.org.ph (2021).

Cabigao (2020) highlighted that, in addition to the roles played by parents and teachers, technology is crucial to closing the learning gaps during this pandemic.

Table 9 presents the parenting gaps among Grade 2 learners in the selected learning areas.

Each statement under parenting gaps was *highly observed*. The parental gap was *highly observed* in each subject area with the following mean: English, 3.56; Filipino, 3.56; Mathematics, 3.51.

The composite mean of knowledge gaps is 3.54 with a standard deviation of 0.723, which means that parental gaps were *highly observed* across learning areas.

Parental gaps are noticeable since most Grade 2 learners do not complete their take-home assignments without the assistance of their parents or guardians. Because

their parents are not involved in school, their eagerness to learn and participation is low. Without their parents' supervision at school, their daily attendance and progress are not noticeable.

Lara and Saracostti (2019) concluded that students with greater academic achievement had medium to high parental participation in their education. In contrast, students with worse academic performance have lower parental involvement in their education. As a result, considerable parental participation is required for children's academic achievement. The study of Cabigao, as cited by Torres (2021), carried out in an elementary school, demonstrated that improved school-home relationships positively affect student performance.

The study conducted by Dargo and Dimas (2021) revealed that they are working, and some had difficulty explaining some topics. Parents did not devote their entire time guiding and aiding their children during modular distance learning.

In addition, Munastiwi and Puryono (2021) stated that parents had difficulty supporting their children due to their hectic schedules and lack of educational knowledge. Meanwhile, Economic instability, unemployment, and shifting work arrangements disproportionately impacted groups in society, with repercussions for parents' capacity to oversee and care for their children's needs (Adams-Prassl et al., 2020).

Table 10 summarizes the gaps observed among Grade 2 learners in selected learning areas.

The gap was *highly observed* in each learning area, with the mean scores gained: 3.65 in English, 3.63 in Filipino, and 3.65 in Mathematics. Gaps were *highly observed* throughout all learning categories, according to the grand mean of gaps, which is 3.64 with a standard deviation of 0.75.

Although all gaps are highly observed, communication, motivation, and skills gaps are among the top three, using a mean of 3.74, 3.71, and 3.70, respectively. This finding is consistent with the previously discovered learning gaps. Since Grade 2 learners have low fundamental skills, motivation, and interest, knowledge, digital, environmental, material, and parental gaps must be enhanced to suffice the basic knowledge and needs of Grade 2 learners across the selected learning areas.

According to an analyst at McKinsey & Company (2021), the pandemic has increased the learning gaps, driving struggling students further away. All stakeholders must be involved in identifying solutions that may be used to close learning gaps among students (Briones and Torio, 2022). According to the findings of the study by Schleicher et al. (2022), this pandemic has awoken schools to a digital environment that is profoundly reshaping learning. In addition, education should think about improving digital literacy in our teachers. Because the crisis has revealed the enormous potential for educational innovation, creating a more supportive environment for educational innovation in schools is critical. Aside from the school's support system, parental involvement at home is critical in closing the gaps.

Part III. Significant Differences in the Gaps Observed in the Selected Learning Areas

Table 11 shows the significant difference in the gaps observed in the selected learning areas.

It reveals that the difference in the gaps among the selected learning areas is not statistically significant ($p = .889 > .05$). This result suggests that the gaps observed in the selected learning areas do not differ. Grade 2 learners experience the same gaps across English, Filipino, and Mathematics subjects.

Borgonovi and Ferrara (2022) stated that the pandemic reduced SES differentials in Math and reading achievement among students with equal achievement, especially among higher-achieving students. Likewise, it reduced gender gaps in Mathematics among higher achievers in (Grade 8. Goudeau et al., 2021) found that school closures have exacerbated achievement gaps linked to social class and ethnicity. (Bielinski et al., 2020) estimated score loss varied by assessment and grade level. Younger students lost more on Reading and Math.

Similarly, Bielinski et al. (2020) found that Math achievement loss was observed across all grades from Kindergarten through Grade 5. As with reading, the estimated losses were greatest in kindergarten. (Goudeau et al., 2021) found that school closures have caused a decrease in Mathematics and language scores, particularly among children from disadvantaged backgrounds.

Part IV. Proposed Learning Recovery Plan Framework to Address the Observed Gaps

The COVID-19 pandemic threw regular school education into disarray, leading to a variety of schooling options. Long school closures lead to gaps in the short term, but they also mean losses in human capital and economic opportunities over the long term. To address this gap, the Basic Education Learning and Recovery Plan (BELRP) should be developed to ensure learners across grade levels can catch up and accelerate their learning and address the socio-emotional and behavioral recovery of learners.

The following are the components of the suggested Learning Recovery Plan Framework. It was suggested in the light of the findings.

The figure shows the Basic Education Learning Recovery Plan Framework entitled Reducing and Averting Gaps for Learning Acceleration: Basic Education Learning Recovery Plan Framework.

As a result of the pandemic, learning challenges resulted in significant gaps for the pupils, as well as poor performance. To address these concerns, the following strategies for implementation were proposed: (1) Technology-Based Instruction (2) Performance and Assessment-Based Activity (3) School-Home Collaboration. These solutions will address the identified challenges to learning and, as a result, will lead to the achievement of the primary goal: Reduce and Avert Gaps

The specific strategies and actions to be taken were enumerated in the crafted School Learning Recovery Action Plan. To ensure the success of the Learning Recovery plan, the school monitoring team will monitor from time to time the proposed plan of the proponents. These solutions will address the identified challenges to learning.

Figure 1. *Learning Recovery Plan Framework*

The Learning Recovery Plan aims to accelerate learning by reducing and averting gaps. Its specific objectives are as follows:

1. Increase learners' interest and participation in the teaching-learning process.
2. Stimulate learners' motivation and build supportive environments.
3. Improve learners' performance in the selected learning areas.

Further, the developed model suggests that technology integration, school-home partnership, and assessment and performance could aid reduce gaps in learning.

Conclusions

1. The Grade 2 learners in Quezon's Third Congressional District perform fairly satisfactorily in English and Mathematics while satisfactorily in Filipino.
 2. Communication, Motivation, Skills, Knowledge, Digital, Environmental, Material, and Parental Gaps are *highly observed* gaps in English, Filipino, and Mathematics which affect their overall performance.
 3. There is no significant difference in the gaps observed in the selected learning areas. Thus, Grade 2 learners have the same gaps in English, Filipino and Mathematics subjects. The hypothesis is accepted.
 4. The Learning Recovery Plan Framework will address performance and gaps of Grade 2 learners in Quezon's Third Congressional District.
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Recommendations

1. The performance level of Grade 2 learners in English and Mathematics is fairly satisfactory while satisfactory in Filipino. Educators may adopt the strategies embedded in this study's Learning Recovery Plan Framework to improve the learner's performance in the selected learning areas.
2. There are observed gaps revealed in this study, teachers' interventions may focus on digital, environmental, material, and parental gaps to leverage the pupils' performance by addressing the observed gaps.
3. Gaps can be seen across the selected learning areas. All stakeholders may collaborate to close these gaps, including the school's support system and parental involvement at home.
4. For learners who did not meet expectation and falls under fairly satisfactory. Innovative Grade 2 teachers may be encouraged to address fundamental learning skills, specifically reinforcing learners' numeracy and literacy skills to accelerate their learning in the selected learning areas.
5. Gaps are affecting performance level of grade 2 learners. Learning Recovery Plan Framework may be used to address gaps and leverage performance in English, Filipino, and Mathematics, as well as other aspects of the teaching and learning process.
6. Future researchers may continue to do research about the learning gaps using the right tool to measure the gaps in learning especially in knowledge gaps. This may help to further explore the gaps that affect learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers adhered to ethical guidelines and standards set forth by relevant institutions and regulatory bodies such as the university and DepEd, such as obtaining approval from ethics committees or review boards. The researchers ensured consent from all participants, including school administrators and other relevant stakeholders, before their involvement in the study. They also provided the participants with clear information about the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits, including the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. Confidentiality and anonymity were also maintained to protect the

privacy of participants to ensure that their responses and personal information were kept secure and not disclosed without their explicit consent. Additionally, the researchers conducted with integrity, honesty, and transparency, avoiding any form of deception or manipulation. The paper passed through a plagiarism check. The result of the study was merely to improve the performance level of the learners. It may contribute to the fast recovery of Philippine Education after Modular Distance Learning.

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